

Effect of Timely Break of Apical Dominance in Specific Cassava Varieties on Their Aboveground Biomass and Root Yield

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Abstract

A study conducted in forested areas in the Democratic Republic of Congo focused on four cassava varieties differing on their typical habits (high, low, and medium branching, as well as erect or unbranched trait). The varieties under study were subjected to four treatments: Topping, Thinning, Combination of topping and thinning, and Control (no topping or thinning), carried out after two months post-transplantation. Topping was about breaking the apical dominance by cutting off the cassava Pekoe plus four young and unfolded leaves, while thinning implied knocking off small stems in favor of the single most robust stem of the plant. Statistical analyses showed significant differences, as regards the behavior of the varieties that underwent topping. Nonetheless, positive effects from topping are dependent on cassava varieties and to their ability to generate new branches from dormant axillary buds. Among involved varieties, greater shoot emergence was noticed on medium-branching Nsansi upon knocking off the terminal bud. Topping happened to elicit a positive outcome on the production of tuberous roots, exemplified by a nearly 39% increase in yield. Besides, reduction of canopy volume through thinning resulted in about 11% decrease in yield.

Keywords: *Topping, Thinning, Leaf biomass, Apical dominance, Axillary bud.*

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Introduction

In cassava plants, topping breaks apical dominance and allows for the emergence of dormant axillary buds. When done at an early growth stage of cassava, it helps the plant generate new basal stems. In turn, as they develop, the latter induce increases in leaf biomass, hence boosting photosynthesis. In tropical areas – where high temperatures and abundant rainfall prevail, such conditions, if well tapped into, can improve cassava root production, based on a sound management of the cassava photosynthetic activity. As a practice, topping thus brings about substantial development of leaf cover, on top of stimulating a greater metabolism which results in higher carbohydrate build-up in the tuberous roots. The onset of leaf development and the formation of the root system take place between 15 and 90 days after planting (DAP) and the highest translocation of carbohydrates towards the roots occurs between 180 and 300 DAP (IITA,1990). During this period, increased levels of dry matter accumulation are observed in the roots and storage takes place, leaf senescence increases, accelerating the rate of leaf fall, and the stem lignifies (Alves et al., 2002). Significant correlations were noted between leaf photosynthesis, total biomass, and root yield (Mabrouk et al., 1990).

In the framework of a study conducted at CIAT/Colombia, maximum photosynthetic CO₂ exchange levels (P_n) of single leaves bunched together were determined for several cassava cultivars selected from different habitats and grown in pots outdoors. P_n rates stood in a narrow range of 22 to 26 μmol CO₂ m⁻²s⁻¹ for all cultivars tested when measured at high photon flux density, and under aerobic conditions, optimum temperature and with low leaf-air vapor pressure differences. For all tested cultivars (9 cvs.), there was a broad optimum temperature for P_n between 25 to 35°C. At temperatures below and above this range, P_n declined in all cultivars with P_n levels reaching 80% of the set maximum, at 20 and 40°C. P_n temperature coefficient (Q₁₀) from 15–25°C was 1.6±0.2 across cultivars (Mabrouk et al., 1990). The topping practice sparks a more substantial development of leaf canopy, thus allowing for improved metabolic process that leads to increased carbohydrate build-up in the roots. In cassava production areas, good yields of tuberous roots are usually obtained when using cultivars that are genetically efficient and resistant or tolerant to the main diseases and pests, as well as good management of cultivation and soil fertility. Therefore, within the context of this study, an analysis was carried out to assess practices likely to either increase or reduce chlorophyll assimilation sometime during the onset of root tuber formation. The undertaking was meant to assess the implications of topping in the possible modifications that photosynthesis can elicit on cassava root yield. To harvest leaves is a normal agricultural operation, mainly in regions where involved leaves are eaten as vegetables. In instances where leaf harvesting is carried out for this purpose, harvesting frequencies are often higher and drastically reduce the volume/quality of elements needed for chlorophyll assimilation, hence the decreases witnessed in root production (Phengvichith et al., 2006, Khuc et al., 2012, Khang 2015).

Thirty to sixty days after planting (DAP), the root swelling process begins, thereby marking the tubers onset (Alves et al., 2002). This occurrence consists of the thickening of secondary creeping roots, which implies that involved roots swell under the cambial effect (Osiro, 1990). The making of tuberous roots intrinsically relates to having a normal root increase in diameter. Topping carried out at the crown level during the early growing stage of the plant coincides with actual start of tuberous roots' formation. At this growth stage of the cassava crop, the abundance of leaves would influence root production by way of availing enough carbohydrates from increased photosynthesis. Production increases are expected if Topping takes place during the first quarter (3-month period) of the cassava growth cycle. Also, increases

in leaf biomass are subject to genetic material (variety), photoperiod, cropping system, and soil fertility, among others. According to (Ekanayake et al., 1998), the photoperiod can also affect the hormonal balance in the plant and may even be responsible for the fluctuation in levels of gibberellic acid (GA) and indoleacetic acid. Most cassava varieties can go through a short-days tuberization process, bearing in mind that overly long days delay the rooting onset, hence limiting production, although helping stimulate cassava's vegetative development. Therefore, the objectives of this study were (i) to investigate the implications of increased leaf biomass during the onset of cassava root tuberization, and (ii) to assess the relationship between increased volume of leaf biomass and increased cassava yield in terms of both fresh and dry weights among various cassava varieties, as per their respective types of 'stem-level' branching.

Materials and Methods

Description of Sites, Soil Properties and Experimental Device

The trials were established in Yangambi (N 0.81823, 24.45841 E, 420 m absl) and in Lito/Kisangani (0.71346, 25.24225, absl 431 m) for two growing seasons (2012-2013 and 2013-2014).

Figure 1. Map Showing the Location of Sites where Trials have been Established (in Lito and Yangambi)
Legend: ■ Forest zone 📍 Locations where trials were established

Both sites are part of an ecosystem of which the climate matches the Af type in the Köppen classification. The average annual rainfall obtained during the cassava cycle is 1,422 mm with 72 days of rain and 1,569 mm with 68 days of rain in Lito and Yangambi, respectively, during the crop year 2012-2013. Regarding the crop year 2013-2014, the rainfalls recorded were 1,681 mm with 84 days of rain in Lito and 1,565 mm with 80 days of rain in Yangambi. Observed rainfalls were distributed throughout the year, with peaks in April and October.

Plant Material

Four varieties differing among themselves – as per their respective intrinsic characteristics – were used. Table 1 (below) provides a description of involved varieties.

Table 1. Surveyed Cassava Varieties as per Their Specific Traits and Production Potentials

	Agronomic traits	Average fresh yield (t. ha⁻¹)	Technical features	Resistance to pests and diseases
Obama	Color: large green leaves; reddish green erect stem; brown tuber skin; Rare or no flowering;	30-45 t. ha ⁻¹ (Station); 20-30 t. ha ⁻¹ (On-farm basis); Leaf Yield: Average	Sweet variety; dry matter approx. 45%; Hydrogen cyanide potential: ≤ 5 mg.100 g-1	Resilience to mosaic, downy mildew, and anthracnose; Susceptible to brown streak; tolerance to green mite, mealybug and root mealybug.
Butamu	Color: broad dark green leaves and light green young leaves; Green leaf stalk; Dark brown stem; Brown tuber skin; Low branching; Flowering at 3 months	25-40 t. ha ⁻¹ (Station), 20-25 t. ha ⁻¹ (On-farm); Low leaf yield	Sweet variety; HCN potential: 5-10mg.100 g-1; Dry matter: 39.5%	Susceptible to diseases; Resilient to mosaic, downy mildew, and anthracnose; Sensitive to pests: Tolerance to green mite.
Nsansi	Color: Broad dark green leaves and light green young leaves; Green and red petioles; White tuber epidermis; White lignified stem; Low branching; Flowering at 3 months.	25-40 t. ha ⁻¹ (Station); 20-25 t. ha ⁻¹ (on the farm); Average leaf yield	Sweet variety; Potential HCN: 5-10mg.100 g-1; Dry matter: 39%	Susceptible to disease; Resistant to mosaic, downy mildew and anthracnose; Susceptible to pests; Tolerant to green mite.
Mbongo	Stem erect; Elongated roots; Dark greenish red stem, with short nodes; Dark green leaves; Red leaf stem; Variety thickens early but retains its dry matter much longer	7-10 t. ha ⁻¹ (Station); 10-15 t. ha ⁻¹ (On-farm); Average leaf yield.	Roots white, soft, relatively fibrous; Dry matter: 38%	100% mosaic sensitive

Source: Mahungu et al. 2021

Vegetation and Soil

The trials took place on fallow lands where herbaceous species – such as *Chromolaena odorata* (L.) R. King & H. Rob., *Panicum maximum* Jacq, *Hypparhenia rufa* (Nees) Stapf and *Pteridium aquilinum* Kuhn – were predominant. In the hinterland of the city of Kisangani (in Litoy), the trial was set up on a site on which previous crop was cassava. The trials for the study were set up immediately after harvesting on the previous crop. Regarding the second experimental site set up in Yangambi, two successive cassava seasons had been conducted on the involved field, prior to trials' establishment.

Soils in Litoy and Yangambi are of a clayey-sandy texture, according to the USDA (US) classification. Proportions of sand are the highest, ranging between 75 and 80%. The fraction of fine particles is low and is estimated between 9 and 20%, while proportions of bigger particles in the said soils stand between 9 and 20% on average. Soils' pH in both Yangambi and Litoy ranged between 4.6 and 4.8. Results from analyzes of involved soils – carried out at the Laboratory of Soil Sciences of the Faculty of Renewable Natural Resources Management [FRNR] at the University of Kisangani (UNIKIS) are presented in Table 2 (Appendix).

Soil Analysis

The organic carbon content is somewhat low at both sites and accounts for 0.075 and 0.082% for Litoy and Yangambi respectively. Phosphorus is more available in the soil of Litoy with 17.67 mg.kg⁻¹ while the related content is low in the soil of Yangambi with 6.6 mg.kg⁻¹. The cation exchange capacity (Ca,

Mg, and K) is quite similar in both sites, nearing 1.9cmol [+] kg⁻¹ for calcium and 0.16 cmol [+] kg⁻¹ for potassium while magnesium related CEC stands at 0.34 and 0.70 for Litoi and Yangambi respectively.

Weather

Located in the Af-type humid zone – according to the Köppen classification –, the respective sites where experimental trials were established recorded monthly rainfalls as detailed below, throughout the crop year 2013-2014.

Table 3. Monthly Precipitation (in mm) During Experimental Testing

Year	Month	Litoi	Yangambi
2013	February	19	87
2013	March	154	151
2013	April	210	170
2013	May	59	157
2013	June	109	116
2013	July	27	134
2013	August	155	150
2013	September	206	180
2013	October	43	214
2013	November	234	209
2013	December	70	180
2014	January	7	102
2014	February	5	122
2014	March	65	161
2014	April	276	175
2014	May	206	153
2014	June	176	113
2014	July	89	109
2014	August	47	156
Total		2157	2839

Experimental Process

The experimental design adopted was a factorial 4x4 split plot with 4 repetitions. The main factor was whether or not the terminal bud was broken (topping) and the reduction in the number of stems per plant (thinning) (4): (i) breaking of apical dominance (topping), (ii) Reduction in the number of stems per plant to leave the most vigorous one (thinning), (iii) thinning + topping and (iv) no treatment (no thinning, no topping).

These operations were carried out 2 months after cassava planting. Topping consisted of cutting the terminal shoot plus four young, unfolded leaves (Figure 2), while thinning was about eliminating the smallest stems to leave only one stem, the strongest one.

Figure 2. Topping Consists of Cutting the Apex Plus the Four Youngest Leaves

The secondary factor implied the four cassava varieties differing by their branching type: (i) Nsansi variety with medium branching (at about 1 m height), Obama variety with an upright trait (does not branch often or at above 1.50 m height), (iii) Butamu variety with low branching (branching between 30 to 50 cm from the ground) and (iv) Mbongo variety (local control with high growth in the study setting) with high branching (branching up to 1.5 meters off the ground). Spacings used were 1 x 1 m and agronomic data – especially regarding the collar’s diameter – was collected on a quarterly basis throughout cassava growth period. At harvest (12 MAP), assessments focused on yield in weight for both fresh and dry matters, the biomass developed, the collar’s diameter on the stems to assert whether thinning had actually influenced the stem development in size. Determination of dry matter content and of the starch content was carried out through specific gravity method in water (Fukuda et al., 2006). This method consists of weighing an approximately 3- to 5-kg sample of fresh cassava freshly harvested from the field, first in the open and, afterwards, while immersed in water.

The values obtained were calculated to obtain the density using the formula below:

$$\text{Specific weight (SW)} = \frac{\text{Weight of cassava roots freshly harvested and weighed in the open}}{\text{Weight in the open} - \text{Weight of the roots immersed in water}} \quad (1)$$

The specific weight obtained was later on converted to obtain dry extracts, in accordance with the Dry matter (%) = 158.3 *SW – 142 formula and the starch content through the Starch (%) = 112.1*SW – 106.4 formula.

The collar’s diameter measurement was taken on a quarterly basis using a digital Vernier from the first quarter. Similarly, canopy diameter was taken on a quarterly basis using a meter shot. Aboveground biomass weight was taken during cassava harvest (at 12 MAP) using a load cell gauge and digital readout device.

Results

Development of the Crown after Breaking Apical Dominance

Based on observations concerning the development of stems after topping and thinning, it appears that Nsansi variety exhibited more sensitivity to apical dominance rupture carried out at 2 MAP. On average, 9 branches were regenerated per plant after topping on this variety which, by nature, branches out between 50 and 80 cm height and has greater capacity to trigger the emergence of axillary buds after topping (Figure 3). This treatment prompted both canopy expansion as well as aboveground biomass weight and volume. Upon topping, Nsansi averages regarding canopy diameter are 186 and 148 cm in Lito and Yangambi respectively, while its canopy got smaller after thinning in Lito (diameter = 103 cm, $p < .01$). Overall, Obama, Butamu and Mbongo varieties did not respond significantly to topping with regards crown development. Some positive effects were noticed on Obama in Lito where the crown diameter reached 139 cm on average after topping. Outcomes were besides different regarding other treatments such as thinning (87 cm in Lito), combination of topping + thinning (91 cm in Lito) and untreated plots (96 cm in Lito). The very same trend was observed on Butamu which exhibited statistically significant values in Lito, with 138 cm in diameter across topped plots.

Aboveground Biomass Weight

Terminal buds breaking off and reduction in the number of stems per plant had an influence on cassava's vegetative development. The effects of such treatments on cassava crops varied based on given varieties. The aerial biomass weight taken at cassava harvest indicated statistically significant differences in Nsansi variety which, subjected to topping, developed abundant biomass averaging 21 kg/foot in Lito and 25.9 kg/foot in Yangambi. The biomass weight averages for Nsansi are 14.2 kg in Lito (LSD.05= 2.17 kg, $P < .01$) and 17.2 in Yangambi (LSD.05= 4, 32 kg, $P < .01$). Upon subjecting the Nsansi variety to thinning, a decrease in its biomass weight was observed, at the rate of around 13.4% and 18.9% respectively in Lito and Yangambi. Some changes were also noted in terms of aboveground biomass weight regarding Obama variety when topped. Under topping, biomass weight reached 11.8 kg in Lito and 7.3 kg in Yangambi. As for the control plots involving Obama variety, the respective means with regards leaf biomass are 7.7 kg in Lito (LSD.05= 2.7 kg, $P < .05$) and 4.9 kg in Yangambi (LSD.05= 1.13 kg, $P < .05$).

Obama – an upright crop variety – was not influenced by the use of the various treatments, as its biomass weight stood between 6 and 11 kg. Besides, in Yangambi, the local variety (Mbongo) exhibited changes in its aboveground biomass weight, especially while subjected to topping on the involved site. The weight was 13.5 kg under topping versus 8.8 kg when no treatment was applied (LSD.05 = 2.1 kg, $p < .01$).

Figure 3. Emergence of Stems on Nsansi (Branching out between 50 and 80 cm off Ground) after Topping in Lito (left) and in Yangambi (right)

Stem Diameter Growth after Thinning and Topping

Observations were also done on cassava stem collar diameters at different growth stages. It was about asserting whether knocking off other stems in favor of the most vigorous one of the crop influenced the development in size of the lone stem. Based on the data collected quarterly regarding cassava harvest, it appears that where thinning was carried out, it led to wider diameters. (At 12 MAP, the thinning made it for diameters to reach 4.1 cm on average in Litoy and 4.3 cm on average in Yangambi, against 3.6 cm on average in Litoy and 3.8 cm on average in Yangambi when no treatment had been applied ($p < .05$)).

Evaluation of Cassava Production in Terms of Fresh and Dry Weight

Performances are obtained after breaking the apical dominance of cassava, by way of conducting topping at 2 MAP e. Ensuing increases in fresh root cassava yields are statistically significant when comparing the cassava varieties under testing. Such conclusions are further asserted on Nsansi variety which, by its nature, branches out soon as it reaches 50 to 100 centimeters height. When topping is carried out on this cassava variety at 2 months after planting, it triggers greater development of the leaf crown by way of regenerating new branches, thereby boosting greater increases in cassava root yield. At the end of the experiments, crop yields neared 50 t. ha⁻¹ while the same kind of yield regarding the very variety was evaluated at 38 t. ha⁻¹ when crops were not topped (31.6%, $p < .001$). In the same vein, increases in yields are observed on other varieties involved, namely Butamu (26.5%, $p < .05$), Obama (11.6%, NS), and Mbongo (9.2%, NS). It is obvious that increased crown diameter upon emergence of dormant buds – subsequent to topping – significantly boosted cassava yields. This is explained by the fact that abundance of leaves increased metabolism which, in turn, led to the production of more carbohydrates in the tuberous roots as a result of the booted photosynthesis taking place in the leaves. Gaps are not significant with regards the yields obtained in line with respective cassava varieties. However, it is during the application of topping that involved varieties could be distinguished from each other. In instances where topping and thinning were combined, thinning did not bring up changes in yield in a statistically significant manner.

Figure 4. Yield in Fresh Cassava Roots as per the Respective Cassava Varieties

It also stems that, when applied alone, thinning leads to decreases in yield in fresh cassava roots. This is explained by the fact that this operation would reduce the leaf surface needed to increase photosynthesis

and meant to favor the formation of tuberous roots. Heeding the surveyed cassava varieties, observations on the Nsansi variety brought us to the conclusion that thinning leads to significant changes in yield (41 t. ha^{-1} , $p < .05$).

The "Topping cum Thinning" combination did not yield significant differences between involved varieties. This further asserts that thinning causes a reduction in leaf volume and therefore does not spark any increase in yield in fresh cassava roots.

Figure 5. Yield in Fresh Cassava Roots as per the Treatments Applied to Cassava Crop 2 Months after Planting (MAP)

Topping and thinning applications on cassava did not result in statistically significant changes in dry matter and starch content in cassava roots. This was observed on all the tested cassava varieties. Dry matter values varied between 33 to 37% depending on the treatments applied and 18 to 20% for starch.

Relationship between Aboveground Biomass and Root Yield

Applying topping at an early stage of cassava root tuberization promotes strong photosynthesis activity and allows for the formation of more carbohydrates to build up starch reserves in the roots. Indeed, this pointed to the fact that increases in weight and volume of aboveground biomass resulted in increased yield in fresh cassava roots. However, the decrease in this aboveground biomass – subsequent to thinning – did lead to a reduction in yield. Recorded averages regarding fresh weight are 38.2 t. ha^{-1} through applying, respectively, topping with a wide canopy of 131.5 kg ($r = 0.98$) and weighing 14.6 kg ($r = 0.97$), 29.7 t. ha^{-1} and combining topping and thinning with 118.6 cm width and canopy 12.4 kg of biomass weight and 19.7 t. ha^{-1} after applying thinning. This treatment reduces the width of the canopy (116 cm) and the weight of aboveground biomass (11.6 kg), which also points to a correlation between canopy width and aboveground biomass weight ($r = 0.92$).

Discussion

Development of the Crown after Breaking Apical Dominance

We came up with statistically significant differences between the application of topping carried out at 2 MAP and the other treatments (thinning, topping + thinning combination, and No treatment). This treatment (topping) gave rise to increase in the volume of the canopy (diameter and weight). Increases of around 24% were obtained in the canopy diameter during topping and 35% in weight of aboveground biomass during the application of the same treatment. Sandifolo et al., 2010 observed an inverse relationship suggesting that the more abundant the leaves, the lesser the root yield. The vigorous growth traits of the Mbundumali variety allowed for the production of much substantial leaf biomass, but this did not lead to higher yield in root and dry matter.

Aboveground Biomass Weight

Topping spurs the emergence of axillary buds and, subsequently, greater development of aboveground biomass in cassava. Nevertheless, reaction to this practice was subject to a given cassava variety involved. It was thus observed that Nsansi variety exhibited the highest production rate regarding the emergence of dormant buds with an average of 7 branches at the location where the topping was carried out, as compared to an average of 2 to 3 branches generated by other involved cassava varieties. The increase in number of branches on Nsansi had also prompted the weight increase in its aboveground biomass, as compared to other varieties. Results obtained by (Ariyo et al. 2010) showed that yield in cassava foliage was significantly different ($P < 0.05$) depending on the harvest periods considered in line with given treatments. For the initial harvest at 2-month growth stage (IC2), the dry matter (DM) yield was the highest, as compared to the second harvest's (H2) and was lower at the fourth harvest (H4) (3.2 and 1.2 tons/ha respectively). In line with the treatment applied at the initial harvest, that is, at 4-month age (CI4), the DM yield was highest during the first harvest (H1) (3.3 tons/ha) and was lowest during the third harvest (H3) (1.2 tons/ha).

Stem Diameter Growth after Thinning and Topping

We noticed positive increases in stem diameter at the collar level when thinning is applied early. However, (Munyahali et al., 2017) observed that leaf harvesting did not yield significant effects on stem height and diameter, as compared to “No harvesting” treatment. Leaf harvesting at 2-WI significantly ($P < 0.05$) decreased both stem height and diameter and resulted in a significant ($P < 0.1$) reduction in stem yield. The noted reduction rate was 20.9% (4.0 t ha^{-1}), as compared to leaf harvest at 4-WI, although only during the second year. Average total biomass and stock root yields regarding the control treatment were 35.8 and 23.5 t ha^{-1} respectively and were not significantly affected by leaf harvesting.

Relationship between Aboveground Biomass and Root Yield

(Sandifolo et al., 2010) observed that, regardless of the type of method used, leaf harvesting significantly reduced cassava roots' yield and dry matter content ($P < 0.001$). Harvesting cassava leaves through thinning method helped producing the highest leaf biomass nearing 25.0 tons fresh weight per hectare, followed by topping (22 t ha^{-1}) and control (9.0 t ha^{-1}). Also, it clearly appeared that in settings/instances where cassava leaves are consumed as vegetables, frequent cassava leaves harvesting does not allow for increases in the volume of aboveground biomass. Instead, it causes most often a decrease in root production. (Mahungu et al., 2021) found that harvesting tender apical leaves and cassava shoots – to be consumed as vegetables – should be discouraged, as it increases the severity of CMD infection across the regenerating cassava shoots, with ensuing reduction in root yield. However, applied at 2 MAP – i.e. at the beginning of cassava root tuberization –, a non-severe leaf harvesting practice sparks/catalyzes greater photosynthesis by way of increasing leaf volume. Thus, it significantly improves cassava root yield as a result of increased carbohydrate accumulation in the root.

Conclusion

We sought to assert whether cassava leaves harvesting practice – very common among cassava growers – would play a role other than the one it is basically known to play, that is, reducing yield in tuberous roots. We found that it is possible to increase yield in cassava roots through a single and less costly cultivation practice, i.e. topping.

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Appendix

Table 2. Soil Properties of the 0-20-cm Layer at the Test Sites

Sites	pH	Organic C (%)	Total N (%)	C/N	Available P (mg.kg ⁻¹)	Exchangeable Ca (cmol[+]kg ⁻¹)	Exchangeable Mg cmol[+]kg ⁻¹)	Exchangeable K (cmol[+]kg ⁻¹)	Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Clay (%)
Litoy	4.80	1.37	0.075	18.27	17.67	1.901	0.336	0.170	77.7	13.5	8.8
Yangambi	4.56	1.40	0.082	17.07	6.60	1,900	0.703	0.155	74.0	9.0	17.0

Table 4. Collar Diameter, Canopy Width, and Aboveground Biomass Weight, Alongside Specific Treatments and Cassava Varieties

Parameters	Cassava varieties	Litoy				Yangambi				Means
		Topping	Thinning	Topping + Thinning	Without treatment	Topping	Thinning	Topping + Thinning	Without treatment	
Collar diameter at 12 MAP (cm)	Obama	4.1 ^{ab}	4.4 ^b	3.9 ^a	3.5 ^a	4.4 ^b	4.7 ^b	4.1 ^{ab}	3.9 ^a	4.1±0.37
	Nsansi	3.7 ^a	4.1 ^{ab}	4.4 ^b	3.4 ^a	4 ^{ab}	4.3 ^b	4.7 ^b	3.7 ^a	4.04±0.43
	Local check	3.9 ^{ab}	4.1 ^{ab}	4.2 ^b	3.9 ^a	4.5 ^b	3.8 ^a	4 ^{ab}	4.2 ^b	4.1±0.23
	Butamu	3.5 ^a	3.9 ^a	3.8 ^a	3.4 ^a	3.8 ^a	4.4 ^b	3.6 ^a	3.5 ^a	3.7±0.32
	Means	3.8±0.26	4.1±0.21	4.1±0.28	3.6±0.24	4.2±0.33	4.3±0.37	4.1±0.45	3.8±0.29	
Width of canopies at 12 MAP (cm)	Obama	121 ^{ab}	87 ^a	91 ^a	96 ^a	139 ^b	117 ^a	127 ^{ab}	133 ^{ab}	113.88±19.99
	Nsansi	186 ^b	103 ^a	136 ^{ab}	120 ^{ab}	148 ^b	126 ^{ab}	148 ^b	126 ^{ab}	136.63±24.87
	Local check	99 ^a	90 ^a	103 ^a	111 ^a	113 ^a	97 ^a	106 ^a	118 ^a	104.63±9.24
	Butamu	138 ^b	117 ^a	110 ^a	124 ^{ab}	108 ^a	110 ^a	128 ^{ab}	100 ^a	116.88±12.41
	Means	136±36.96	99.3±13.72	110±19.03	112.8±12.42	127±19.51	112.5±12.23	127.3±17.15	119.3±14.22	
Average weight of biomass	Obama	11.8 ^b	7.3 ^a	12.1 ^b	13.3 ^b	15.7 ^b	14.4 ^b	12.5 ^b	11.8 ^{ab}	12.36±2.46
	Nsansi	21 ^c	13.4 ^b	17.4 ^{bc}	15.1 ^b	25.9 ^c	18.9 ^b	20.4 ^c	17.4 ^b	18.69±3.86

leaves and green stems per foot at 12 MAP (Kg)	Local check	9.5 ^a	10.1 ^a	8.7 ^a	10.8 ^a	13.5 ^b	9.1 ^a	11.1 ^{ab}	8.8 ^a	10.2±1.60
	Butamu	8.2 ^a	5.5 ^a	7.5 ^a	6.8 ^a	10.9 ^a	7.7 ^a	9.6 ^a	8.4 ^a	8.08±1.65
	Means	12.63±5.78	9.08±3.45	11.43±4.43	11.5±3.59	16.5±6.57	12.53±5.14	13.4±4.81	11.6±4.15	

